

**Special Issue
“EHMA 2023 Abstract Book”**

Guest Editors: Prof. Sandra C. Buttigieg, MD; Prof. Americo Cicchetti; Prof Axel Kaehne; Dr Alexandre Lourenço; Dr Teppo Heikkilä, MD, EMBA; Prof Todorka Kostadinova; Dr Eszter Kovacs; Prof Federico Lega; Prof Ann Mahon; Dr Rui Dang; Nabil Jamshed MSc MBA BBA; Prof Dr Marija Jevtic, MD; Prof Dr Teresa Magalhães; Prof Dr Henk Nies; Prof Mag Dr Manfred Pferzinger; Prof Dr Rui Santana; Dr Federica Morandi; Mr George Valiotis

[Introduction to the Special Issue](#)

Prof. Sandra C. Buttigieg, Prof. Americo Cicchetti

Abstracts in the Special issue

[Experiencing and witnessing disruptive behaviours towards nurses in COVID-19 teams, patient safety and errors in care](#)

Dr Gillie Gabay, Dr Sigal Shfran-Tikva, Prof Avi Kluger, Ms Liron Asraf

[Towards sustainable health workforces: the roles of governance, planning and data](#)

Dr Gareth H Rees, Mr Cris Scotter, Dr Rosemary James, Mr Levan Samadashvili

[Workplace ostracism undermines work well-being in healthcare](#)

Ms Sirpa M. Manninen, Prof Sanna Laulainen, Prof Timo Sinervo, Mr Samuli Koponen

[Utilising dormant workforce talent: developing, supporting & integrating multinational doctors in England through the medical support worker \(MSW\) programme, a sustainable workforce initiative](#)

Dr William Sacre, Dr Rachel Rajadurai, Mr Thomas Kearney, Dr Ivan Trotman, Mr Manraj Dignpal, Dr Celia Ingham Clark

[A realist review of the international literature demonstrating how governance and decision-making during the 2008 financial crisis impacted health workforce resilience for COVID-19 and future health system shocks](#)

Dr Padraic Fleming, Dr Louise Caffrey, Dr Sara VanBelle, Dr Sarah Barry, Dr Sara Burke, Ms Jacki Conway, Dr Rikke Siersbaek, Mr David Mockler, Prof Steve Thomas

[The role of governance modes in dealing with complexity of healthcare systems: evidence from three regions in Italy](#)

Dr Natalia Oprea, MSc Gianmario Cinelli, MSc Michela Bobini, Prof Francesco Longo, Prof Mario Del Vecchio

About the EHMA Conference

The EHMA Conference is Europe's preeminent conference on health management. Each year it gathers the full healthcare ecosystem, including health managers and leaders, healthcare professionals, researchers, academics, industry representatives, and decision-makers from Europe, and beyond.

The EHMA Conference provides a platform to discuss the latest health management research, tools and evidence from renowned researchers, academics and professionals. It is concerned on translating research into practice. It creates opportunities for dialogue and exchange on solutions to ensure the sustainability and resilience of health systems.

The EHMA 2023 Annual Conference

EHMA 2023 is the 28th edition of our Annual Conference.

This year's conference theme is 'Health management: sustainable solutions for complex systems'. Three years of the COVID pandemic have exposed gaps and vulnerabilities in European health systems, and the immense pressure on the health and care workforce. Sustainable solutions and strategic thinking are needed to drive the transformation of health systems.

EHMA 2023 is structured around five tracks that reflect the holistic practice of health management, and frame the lenses through which contemporary topics are analysed and discussed.

The European Health Management Association

The European Health Management Association (EHMA) strives for excellent health management for a healthy Europe by supporting the spread of knowledge on effective health management practices. Active since 1982, EHMA exists so that Europe's citizens and communities can benefit from quality, safe, value-based care and health systems.

Our focus is on enhancing the capacity and capabilities of health management to deliver high-quality healthcare and support the successful implementation of health policy. Our commitment is on supporting the provision of data and research findings for evidence-based decision-making and monitoring health policies and practices.

EHMA is the only membership organisation in Europe to bring together the full health management ecosystem, including health and hospital managers, healthcare professionals, researchers, academia, policy and decision-makers. We are a recognised and respected amplifier of best practices in the evolution of health management, and we provide an environment where evidence, challenge and experience are valued and complex debates on current topics can take place.

Sustainable solutions in climate action by strengthening the role of Medical Doctors

Prof Dr Çiğdem Çağlayan¹, Dr Melike Yavuz², Ms Funda Gacal³, Prof Dr Marija Jevtic^{4,5}, Ms Anne Stauffer⁶

¹*Kocaeli University, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Public Health, Turkey.* ²*Bahçeşehir University, Faculty of Medicine; HASUDER – the Association of Public Health Specialists in Turkey, Turkey.* ³*Health and Environment Alliance (HEAL), Turkey.* ⁴*University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina, Serbia.* ⁵*Université Libre de Bruxelles (ULB), Research centre on Environmental and Occupational Health, School of Public Health, Belgium.* ⁶*Health and Environment Alliance (HEAL), Belgium*

Climate change and its health effects have been a growing concern among health professionals and the healthcare sector. Sustainable solutions in climate action demand a systematic approach in the healthcare sector, new procedures, and important infrastructure investments to strengthen preparedness and resilience. But the most important task in this process is to achieve the best possible preparedness of health professionals themselves.

This study aimed to measure the awareness, perception, and knowledge of health professionals about climate change, and to examine the factors which shape their position and level of awareness.

The research population of this descriptive study consists of medical doctors from Turkey, Serbia and EUPHA-ENV members. The data were collected with an online-questionnaire consisting of 29 questions in total, prepared by the researchers in line with the information obtained by the literature search.

This study was carried out within the scope of the Collaboration Project for Environment, Climate and Health (ÇİSİP) funded by the European Union. Ethical approval was obtained with the decision numbered 2021-06/04 of Bahçeşehir University Clinical Research Ethics Committee.

In spring 2023, more than 400 participants (medical doctors) from Turkey, Serbia and from the other countries in the European region responded to the survey. Survey questions included their perception on climate change impacts and the increase of extreme weather events, their concern about climate change, and the role of health professionals in climate mitigation and adaptation.

The awareness, perception and knowledge of the health care workers participating in our study on the health effects of climate change were found to be high in general. Health professionals participating in this study think that their colleagues have an important role in the health effects of climate change.

In general, medical doctors think that the health sector should be concerned about this issue and that effective measures can be taken, but the sector is not yet sufficiently prepared for the health effects of climate change.

Using the investigation about awareness, knowledge, and perception of medical doctors on climate change and its health effects we can establish necessary steps towards sustainable solutions in climate action, by strengthening the role to medical doctors through education, by appreciating needs, responsibilities and opinions in their role according to climate change issues.